

HIGHER EDUCATION MARKETING: MAPPING OF BUDDHIST HIGHER EDUCATION CUSTOMERS (MULTI-SITE CASE STUDY)

WIDIA DARMA ¹, NURHATTATI FUAD ² and MATIN ³

^{1,2,3} Jakarta State University.

Email: ¹widiadharna91@gmail.com, ²nurhattati@unj.ac.id, ³matin@unj.co.id

ABSTRACT :

This study aimed to determine how the Buddhist Religious College (PTKB) mapped higher education customers. This study used a multi-site qualitative research method. The data collection technique used observation, interview, and documentation studies in this research. The research was conducted at two PTKB, namely STABN Raden Wijaya and STIAB Smaratungga. The results of the findings of this study were 1) PTKB has not carried out customer mapping systematically 2) No survey or research has been carried out related to the needs and expectations of customers 3) The use of the latest technology has not been used in mapping customers or prospective new students.

Keywords: Education Marketing Management, Higher Education Customers, Mapping customers

1. Introduction

This research was appointed starting from the researchers' interest in seeing the problems that occur in Buddhist Higher Education (PTKB), especially related to the implementation of PTKB marketing to be able to socialize and communicate the existence of high schools, as well as special programs that are owned to be well received by the higher education consumers themselves. Implementing higher education marketing is considered an important part of increasing the quantity of prospective new students for higher education. Moreover, marketing education is the main key in global competition; competition between higher education continues to exist.

Based on a preliminary study conducted by researchers at the STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya and STIAB Smaratungga, the researchers found a decline in the interest of prospective students in Buddhist religious studies programs. It is certainly interesting to do an in-depth study because the existence of a university is not only seen from the quality but also the quantity of students who study at the university. Therefore, to continue to exist and grow, higher education institutions need to continue to adapt and innovate to increase the interest of prospective students.

Global developments encourage institutions to adapt to such rapid changes quickly. However, changes in lifestyle, social, and culture need to be followed by making innovations in managing a higher education institution so that it still exists and can compete and thrive. The globalization of higher education directly impacts the increasingly intense competition between universities, especially in Indonesia. The fundamental problem is optimizing quality and quantity, which must go hand in hand (Syakur & Panuju, 2020) .

According to (Veseli & Kurtishi, 2017), educational marketing strategy is an important part of an institution to communicate and convey messages to individuals, groups, or the whole community to align their interests and desires. Today marketing is at the forefront of activities, mostly for higher education institutions (Fagerstom & Ghinea, 2013) . Marketing is an important area in educational institutions, so they must initiate appropriate promotional policies to encourage targets to accept the services offered (Ogunnaike, 2014) . Currently, marketing is the main thing (Kirp, 2004) .

Higher education has different consumers and targets. Different stakeholders have different needs, so the quality of Higher Education Institutions, their services, and customer satisfaction are very important (da Nóbrega, 2017) . It was further explained that in doing marketing, what needs to be done is to understand the segmentation and targets to be reached. Segmentation is a criterion of the promotion target itself influenced by the homogeneity of community groups, lifestyles, needs, and motives. With the segmentation classification, the target will be analyzed and understood optimally.

Chart 1: Targeting

Source: (da Nóbrega, 2017)

To carry out effective and appropriate marketing, an initial step is needed to map higher education customers, especially Buddhist higher education. In-depth analysis and study related to higher education customers are required quantitatively and qualitatively. A complete and comprehensive picture of higher education customers needs to identify higher education customers in-depth, structure, and continuity. One of the newest paradigms to better understand customers is customer journey mapping (Lemon & Verhoef, 2016) .

Buddhist religious colleges with the majority segmentation of the Buddhist community need to have valid data related to Buddhist religious higher education customers. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis and presentation of data are needed to formulate the right marketing strategy to increase the interest of prospective new students at Buddhist religious colleges,

especially at STABN Raden Wijaya and STIAB Smaratungga. According to (Pharr, 2018), Customer Experience Management (CXM) is a complex multidimensional process that integrates several important customer-oriented marketing processes, including consumer decision processes, satisfaction, customer relationship management, customer relationship management, and customer journey mapping.

It has been further explained that customer mapping can be divided into three phases, namely 1) pre-purchase phase, defined as "prospect," which is the phase where customers or prospective students are introduced as targets. 2) the purchase phase, in this case, can be interpreted as a phase or stage when you have entered into a student at a college, 3) the post-purchase phase can be interpreted as when they have become alumni of a college.

Figure 1: A Sample Student Journey Map

Source: (Pharr, 2018)

Given the significance of mapping higher education customers as an indicator of the success of higher education marketing, this study investigates the steps and policies implemented by Buddhist religious universities, particularly STABN Raden Wijaya and STIAB Smaratungga, both of which are located in Central Java.

2. Research methods

2.1 Research Design

This research used the case study method. A case study is a detailed examination of one setting, subject, document storage area, or particular event (Bogdan & Biklen, 1992). Using this case study method is to understand real-life phenomena in-depth. However, such an understanding includes important contextual conditions because they are closely related to the phenomenon of study (Yin, 2009). There are three types of qualitative case studies: single instrumental case studies, collective or multiple case studies, and intrinsic case studies (Creswell, 2007).

This study used multiple sites to be carried out by empirically investigating phenomena in real life. However, when the boundary between the phenomenon and the context was not visible, the sources of data and facts were used through analysis. The main characteristic of a multi-site study is when the researcher examines two or more subjects, settings, or data storage locations.

2.2 Research Informants

The informants or resource persons used in this study involved several informants at the level of policymakers or implementers. The following were research informants' data;

Table 1: Research Informants

No	Informant	Position	Code
STABN Raden Wijaya			
1	Hariyanto	Deputy Head of Administration	SRW-WK2-1
2	Marjianto	Deputy Head of Student Affairs	SRW-WK3-2
3	Manggala Wirya Tantra	head of program Dharmaduta	SRW-PMB1-3
4	Adi Nugroho	lecturer /Computer Setup	SRW-BIT1-4
STIAB Smaratungga			
5	Bhante Dithisanpanno	Head of STIAB Smaratungga	SMR-KET-1
6	Sugiyanto	Head of Buddhist Religious Education Study Program	SMR-KPS1-2
7	Mujiyanto	Lecturer	SMR-DOS1-4

Source: Researcher Findings

2.3 Data collection procedures and techniques

The research procedure used in this study consisted of several research steps using the Robert K. Yin case study method: research planning, research design, research preparation, research data collection, research data analysis, and research report preparation. The research analysis was carried out with a pairing pattern. It tested the validity of the data through triangulation of data sources and triangulation of techniques. In analyzing the data, the researcher used the concept developed by Miles and Huberman as consisting of three paths, namely data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions or verification. The three activities used an interactive model as follows:

Figure 2: Data Analysis of Miles and Huberman's Interactive Model

Source: Miles, MB, & Huberman, AM (1992)

Research Results and Discussion

STABN Raden Wijaya is the only State Buddhist campus in Central Java. As stated in the history section, the STABN Raden Wijaya campus has a long history before becoming a state campus in 2011. Initially, STABN Raden Wijaya opened three religious study programs: Buddhist Counseling, Buddhist Religious Education, and Buddhist Religious Education. Then in 2019, STABN Raden Wijaya opened three new study programs open to the public, namely Buddhist Tourism, Buddhist Communication Studies, and School Teacher Education Basic (PGSD) Buddhism.

STIAB Smaratungga is one of the oldest Buddhist universities in Indonesia. STIAB Smaratungga is a private Buddhist college in Central Java. STIAB Smaratungga currently has one study program for undergraduate and one post-graduate study program. Both of the study programs have a scientific concentration on Buddhist religious education. The campus has special characteristics in the management of higher education. It can be seen how the role of members of the Sangha or the monks and nuns in teaching and management in Buddhist higher education.

1. Customer Mapping at STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya

To sustain success in increasing student interest within the scope of Buddhist higher education, a real picture is needed regarding the segmentation and market of higher education. Identifying prospective students needs to be done in detail as an initial part before planning college marketing. Identification of Buddhist religious higher education customers is the main foundation for obtaining a comprehensive picture related to higher education customers. Buddhist Universities need to identify and analyze the existence of customers, ranging from location, social conditions, geographical location, expectations and needs of customers, and psychological symptoms that appear in higher education customers.

Based on research in the field, STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya has a fairly broad market or educational customers. STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya not only has students who are limited to one religion, namely Buddhism, but has penetrated the market or a wider market after the general study program was opened in 2019. General study programs that anyone can access are not limited to Buddhists. There are three general study programs: Buddhist Tourism, Buddhist PGSD, and Buddhist Communication Studies. With a wider scope of education customers, STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya has a greater opportunity to continue to increase the number of students.

The research results at STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya Wonogiri indicated that mapping education customers had not been carried out optimally. A comprehensive description of the data on the distribution of prospective students, surveys, and research directly related to prospective students are still insignificant. The data collection process for prospective students or descriptions related to the number and distribution of higher education customers had not been recorded nor documented. What has happened so far at STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya Wonogiri has estimated certain areas that are considered to have the potential to produce new student candidates. The location is considered to have a large population or number of Buddhists, so a

promotion team will be formed to target these areas. It is as conveyed by the resource person during the interview as follows;

yes, there is no prospective student mapping students in detail. Usually, it is just a rough idea, certain locations that we think have an interest (SRW-WK2-1, 2021)

Based on this statement, it can be seen that the mapping aspect of higher education customers has not been carried out optimally, where higher education institutions have complete data and information related to prospective students or education customers that have not been recorded or carried out optimally.

It was further explained that STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya Wonogiri had never conducted a survey or analysis related to the needs and expectations of higher education customers. So far, what was done was related to surveys of graduates and graduate users. As stated by the vice-chairman of student affairs, as follows;

Surveys related to prospective students have not been carried out. So far, what has been done is related to the tracer study conducted by UP2M (SRW-WK3-2, 2022).

A planned, measurable, and comprehensive mapping has not been carried out based on research conducted by researchers related to the mapping of higher education customers at STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya Wonogiri, where higher education institutions do not yet have data related to prospective students such as quantitative data for prospective students, market maps, and data related to the hopes and desires of Buddhist higher education customers, especially at STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya Wonogiri.

2. Customer Mapping at STIAB Smaratungga

STIAB Smaratungga has students spread across various regions in Indonesia. In general, students at STIAB Smaratungga come from the island of Java. However, STIAB Smaratungga, with a Buddhist Religious Education study program and a Masters in Buddhist Religious Education course, has a specific target market: prospective Buddhist students. The number of adherents of Buddhism is quite large in Central Java, especially in Temanggung, Jepara, Pati, Semarang and Kebumen, and Banjarnegara.

Based on research in the field through observations and interviews and a study of documentation, the number of students at STIAB Smaratungga is quite large compared to the other two PTKB in Central Java with Buddhist Religious Education study programs. The average per batch reaches more than 20 students. Based on observations, it was found that the students at STIAB Smaratungga can be divided into two categories, namely students as householders or students in general, and there is a category of students who live in dormitories or monasteries to become Samanara. The novices here are meant for students who, apart from being students as usual, also practice exploring the spiritual life by wearing robes, and living in monasteries or dormitories to explore the teachings of Buddhism.

Customers or prospective students from STIAB Smaratungga are only limited to Buddhists. At STIAB Smaratungga, there is only one Buddhist Religious Education study program and one post-graduate master's degree one Buddhist Religious Education study program with a

Buddhist market. This specific and limited market is different from campus or college with a more diverse market and from various circles of society. In terms of mapping customers or prospective students, the results in the field show that customer mapping and analysis related to prospective new students have not been carried out optimally, this is as stated by the Chair of STIAB Smaratungga in an interview excerpt as follows;

Yes, it doesn't seem like it's possible to do customer mapping. Then surveys or research related to customer mapping studies also seem to have not been carried out until now. There is no quantitative data. For example, how many are like that in this area, not yet (SMR-KET-1,2021)

Based on the explanation of the excerpt from the interview with the Chairperson of STIAB Smaratungga, it can be seen that the mapping of customers or prospective students at STIAB Smaratungga has not been carried out optimally. There is no activity in the form of surveys or research to determine the condition of customers and data collection on customers or prospective students both quantitatively and qualitatively. The same thing was conveyed by the head of the Buddhist Religious Education study program as in the following interview excerpt;

To do customer mapping or analysis, we haven't done it optimally. Likewise, for surveys and research, we haven't done it. Usually, we do surveys for alumni, such as study tracers, but not for prospective new students (SMR-KPS 1 -2, 2021) .

Based on these two opinions, it is explained that the mapping or analysis related to the mapping of customers or prospective new students has not been carried out optimally. Therefore, data related to the potential market distribution, expectations, and desires of higher education customers have not been collected or owned by STIAB Smaratungga.

Based on the research, both at the STAB Negeri Raden Wijaya Campus and STIAB Smaratungga, it was found that customer mapping has not been carried out optimally by higher education institutions. To get maximum results in marketing higher education, comprehensive information is needed regarding the circumstances and conditions of Buddhist higher education customers. A more consumer-oriented approach to Marketing, providing greater choice, delivering true value, and winning the hearts and minds of consumers are the keys to long-term market advantage (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2016)

Marketing must find innovative and advanced strategies to deal with increasingly fierce competition, society's complexities, and changing needs. To help its progress, Marketing has utilized disciplines such as psychology, sociology, economics, and anthropology to be more effective (Irene, 2009) . Buddhist higher education institutions need to conduct in-depth analysis and studies related to a concrete picture of higher education customers so that the formulation of an appropriate and effective marketing strategy will be obtained. Research involving the latest technology is needed to obtain data related to the condition of higher education customers. A scalable, structured, and well-organized customer analysis and mapping are required.

Higher education customers are constantly evolving. Along with the times and the development of the paradigm and the social conditions of the community, it is necessary to understand that the perspectives and attitudes of education customers continue to change. Thus, it is also necessary for higher education institutions to formulate appropriate approaches and strategies to reach and distribute information to higher education customers. According to a report from the Organization for Economic Co-Operation And Development (OECD, 2009), Consumer education changes from time to time.

Figure 3: The evolution of consumer education

Source: Organization For Economic Co-Operation And Development (OECD, 2009)

Mapping of Buddhist religious higher education customers needs to be done systematically and continuously to dig up more comprehensive information and accommodate the aspirations and expectations of customers while providing quality services. In addition, land mapping by higher education institutions needs to use the role and use of technology in collecting and analyzing data related to maps of higher education customers that currently have not been carried out by Buddhist higher education institutions.

Based on the research results at the STABN Raden Wijaya Wonogiri, it was found that customer mapping had not been carried out optimally by higher education institutions, both quantitative and qualitative mapping. The mapping was carried out while still referring to general information about locations considered potential as markets for higher education institutions.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion above, it can be concluded into several points of research findings at STABN Raden Wijaya and STIAB Smartungga; 1) PTKB has not carried out customer mapping optimally 2) No survey or research has been conducted regarding the needs and expectations of customers 3) Technology has not been used to map customers or prospective new students.

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